

Online Sequential Extreme Learning Machine (OSELM) based Q-learning(OSELM-QL)

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ABSTRACT

The usage of reinforcement learning (RL) for many type of applications is increasing. The quick development of machine learning models in the recent years has motivated researchers to integrate Q-learning with deep learning which has opened the door for many vision based applications of RL. However, using RL with shallow types of neural network has not been tackled adequately in the literature despite its need for real time types of applications such as control systems or time constraint decision based system. In this article, we propose a novel online sequential extreme learning machine OSELM based RL using Q-learning named as OSELM-QL. In OSELM-QL, the role of the neural network NN is to learn the best criterion for selecting the action based on Q value for exploitation or select the action randomly for exploration. For validation, we compare the predicted Q values by NN to show its feasibility to operate as an assistant sub-block to classical Q-learning for balancing between exploration and exploitation. The convergence is proved in the simulation model. This emphasizes on the potential of using this approach as an assistant block in the standard Q-learning system for exploration and exploitation balancing.

KEYWORDS: Reinforcement learning; Q-learning; online sequential extreme learning machine; neural network.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent time neural network and machine learning have emerged with wide range of applications [1]–[4]. Reinforcement Learning (RL) is one category of

machine learning models that consider two separated entities: a time-variant environment and an agent. The environment is described by its states while the agent has to perform actions that change the environment states and receives rewards based on the action state association. The agent aims at maximizing cumulative reward based on an invented policy. Thus, each RL model has to be represented based on: reward, possible set of actions, and possible states. The state is created in the agent based on its sensory information about the environment [5].

In recent years, numerous applications were resolved by using the technology of RL. Some of the significant applications of RL is networks load balancing and routing. RL was used to perform load balancing in the application of deployment of multiple software defined networks SDN controllers. RL can perform optimal selecting of switch migration triples, to attain the global optimal controller load balancing with minimum cost [6],[7]. Also it was applied for routing to make the best choice among the neighbors at any moment to transmit a packet to the destination to predicting the behavior pattern of the nodes in relation to the target node [8],[9] or to improve the message deliver ratio with minimum possible delay and hops [10],[11]. RL has also proved its powerful capability in solving other types of engineering problems. In robotics field, RL was used to perform autonomous landing of quadrotor on a moving platform [12], to control the balance of legged robots [13], or to predict time series [14],[15]. Some researchers have explored the ability of integrating conventional Q-learning with other artificial intelligence for increasing the performance of the learning such as the work of [16] where genetic was integrated with reinforcement learning.

The speed of learning in the RL models is becoming a concern models especially with the growing of using the deep topology of NN that is used to approximate the RL Q value [17]. Very few models have concentrated on shallow based RL due to the concern of universal approximation. Extreme learning machine, which is one hidden layer neural network with arbitrary number of neurons in the hidden layer has been proved to be a universal approximator [18]. This motivates using it as Q function approximator in RL. The goal of this article is to develop online extreme learning machine based RL and prove its effectiveness in various RL problems, load balancing and control[19]–[22].

The remaining of the article is organized as follows. A background is provided in section 2. Next, the related works are given in section 3. Afterwards, the methodology is provided in section 4. Next, the evaluation and experimental works are given in section 5. Finally, a conclusion and future work are given in section 6.

2. BACKGROUND

This section provides the needed background for the methodology. It is presented in three (3) subsections. In sub-section 2.1, we provide a summary of RL definition and Q-learning. Next, in sub-section 2.2, we present extreme learning machine ELM. Subsection 2.3 provides the background of the online extreme learning machine.

2.1. Reinforcement Learning and Q-learning

A typical approach in RL is Q-learning which is considered as the state of the art in RL. Q-learning does not need a prior model for the environment, alternatively, the agent performs an exploration and an exploitation to learn its optimal policy. The concept of Q-learning is to allow to the agent to calculate Q –value for each state-action pair. This is done iteratively in each time instant t , where the agent observes the environment and update the corresponding state s_t , selects the action a_t that maximizes the cumulative reward in instant $t + 1$. The equation (1) of updating Q value is given as:

$$Q(s_t, a_t) = Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha[r_{t+1} + \gamma \max_a (Q(s_{t+1}, a_{t+1}) - Q(s_t, a_t))] \quad (1)$$

This equation is enabled based on ε according to this condition: generate a random number between 0 and 1. In case the random number is lower than ε then apply (1), otherwise, selection random action. Once the value of ε is defined, then a decay factor named as epsilon decay $d \varepsilon$ is applied.

2.2. Extreme Learning Machine

Extreme learning machine [18], [23] is a training algorithm for one hidden layer neural network. The number of neurons N_L in the hidden layer is assumed to be arbitrary. However, changing the number of hidden neurons implies a change in the performance. On the other side, each neuron has an activation function $g(x)$ which can be tansig, sigmoid, radial basis function, or other. The input vector is $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N)$ while the output vector is Y . The weights between the input and output is $w = (w_i, b_i)$ where $i = 1, 2 \dots N_L$ where w_i represents the weights the connects between the input vector and the neuron while b_i denotes the bias of the neurons b_i . The output matrix is $H(X, w, g)$. The training is done using the algorithm presented in Table1. It is combined of three steps: random initialization of weights in the input hidden layer in 2, calculation of output matrix in 3, and calculation of hidden output weights using Moore Penrose equation in (4).

Table 1. Pseudocode of ELM

Input	
Data={x,y}	// Labeled Data
Nl	//number of hidden neurons
g	//type of activation function
Output	
(w,b,beta)	//weights for NN
Start	
1.featureSize=numberOfCulunms(x);	
2. (w,b)=genRandom(Nl,featureSize);	
3. H=calculateH(x,w,b);	
4. beta=moore_penrose(H)*y;	

End

2.3. Online sequential extreme learning machine OSELM

Online sequential extreme learning machine [24] is an online variant of ELM in which data is assumed to be combined of chunks $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - \tilde{N} - 1$. The algorithm works based on updating the weights in an iterative way without the need to store older chunks of data. Whenever a new chunk arrives, the weights are updated based on the older chunk data.

Given $H\beta = T$, $H_0 = [h_1 \dots h_{\tilde{N}}]^T$ is defined and it refers to the sub-matrix comprising of the first \tilde{N} rows of H , where $\text{rank}(H) = \text{rank}(H_0) = \tilde{N}$, and $T_0 = [t_1 \dots t_{\tilde{N}}]^T$.

Step 1 Calculate the initial value $M_0 = (H_0^T H_0)^{-1}$ and $\beta^{(0)} = M_0 H_0^T T_0$.

Step 2 for each h_{k+1} ($(\tilde{N} + K + 1)$ -th row of H) and $t_{k+1} = T_{(\tilde{N}+k+1)}^T$, estimate

$$M_{k+1} = M_k - \frac{M_k h_k + 1 h_k^T + 1 M_k}{1 + h_{k+1}^T M_k h_{k+1}} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta^{(k+1)} = \beta^{(k)} + M_{k+1} h_{k+1} (t_k^T - h_{k+1}^T \beta^{(k)}) \quad (3)$$

Where $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N - \tilde{N} - 1$.

Step 1 Booting Phase: Considering a small initial training set $= \{(x_i, t_i) | x_i \in R^n, t_i \in R^m, i = 1 \dots, \tilde{N}\}$ to start the learning algorithm first through the following boosting procedure:

Assign arbitrary input weight W_i and bias b_i or center μ_i and impact width $\sigma_i = 1, \dots, \tilde{N}$.

Calculate the initial hidden layer output matrix $H_0 = [h_1, \dots, h_{\tilde{N}}]^T$, where $h_i = [g(w_1 \cdot X_i + b_1), \dots, g(W_{\tilde{N}} \cdot X_i + b_{\tilde{N}})]^T, i = 1, \dots, \tilde{N}$.

Estimate the initial output weight $\beta^{(0)} = M_0 H_0^T T_0$, where $M_0 = (H_0^T H_0)^{-1}$ and $T_0 = [t_1, \dots, t_{\tilde{N}}]^T$.

Set $k = 0$.

Step 2 Sequential Learning Phase: for each further coming observation (X_i, t_i) , where, $X_i \in R^n, t_i \in R^m$ and $i = \tilde{N} = 1, \tilde{N} + 2, \tilde{N} + 3, \dots$, do

Calculate the hidden layer output vector $h_{(k+1)} = [g(W_1 \cdot X_1 + b_1), \dots, g(W_N \cdot X_i + b_N)]^T$.

Calculate latest output weight $\beta^{(k+1)}$ based on RLS algorithm:

$$M_{k+1} = M_k - \frac{M_k h_{k+1} h_{k+1}^T + 1 M_k}{1 + h_{k+1}^T M_k h_{k+1}} \quad (4)$$

$$\beta^{(k+1)} = \beta^{(k)} + M_{k+1} h_{k+1} (t_k^T - h_{k+1}^T \beta^{(k)}) \quad (5)$$

Set $k = k + 1$

The pseudocode of OSELM is given in Table 2. The algorithm is combined of two phases: the first phase is a boosting phase while the second one is the sequential learning phase. In the boosting phase, the three steps of calculating the input hidden layer weights, the output matrix, and the hidden output weights are repeated. In the phase an update of the output weights is carried out at every step using the recursive(5).

Table 2. Pseudocode of OSELM

Onput	
Data={xi,yi}	// Labeled
Data,i=1,2...N	
NI	//number of hidden
neurons	
g	//type of activation
function	
f1,f2	//pre-defined equations
Output	
(w,b,beta)	//weights for NN
Start	
1. featureSize=numberOfCulunms(x);	
2. //boosing phase	
3. (w,b)=genRandom(NI,featureSize);	
4. h0=calculateH(x0,w0,b0);	
5. beta=moore_penrose(H0)*y0;	
6. //iterative phase (recursive equation)	
7. for k=1 until N	
8. h(k)=calculateH(x(k),w(k),b(k));	
9. m(k)=f1(h(k),h(k-1),m(k-1))	
10. beta(k)=f2(h(k),m(k),beta(k-1))	
End	
11. beta=beta(k+1);	
End	

3. RELATED WORKS

Some researchers have adapted Q-learning according to the application they aim to solve. In the work of [25], the authors have adapted state action reward state action (SARSA) algorithm [26] to use it in solving the congestion control method of SDN data center based on reinforcement learning. In their modification, the algorithm does not rely only on R matrix for selecting the action, but it relies on the route of the current flow for load balancing with adding the congestion judgement. This modification is not really a theoretical in the context of RL, rather, it is an application need. A concern has been raised by researchers about the speed of learning in RL [17]. Basically, the backpropagation approach is used for training NN based RL, however, it suffers from slow convergence and being subject to local minima in many cases. About the speed of learning in RL [17]. Basically, the backpropagation approach is used for training NN based RL, however, it suffers from slow convergence and being subject to local minima in many cases.

Therefore, some researchers have proposed some theoretical modification to RL. In the work of [27], the assistance of neural network, namely extreme learning machine ELM, was proposed for approximating the Q-function in Q-learning. Furthermore, the researchers have solved the problem of increasing number of samples by incorporating a rolling time-window. This increases the efficiency of RL even with the increase of the number of samples. Their method was evaluated on the famous boat problem [28]. ELM uses a different approach of training than BP. While NN in BP is trained using the gradient of the error in an iterative way, ELM uses one iteration based training which makes it faster than conventional BP based approaches. The limitation of shallow structure of ELM was solved by developing RL models based on hierarchal ELM. In the work of [29], the approach of random based training instead of iterative based was used for deep model with the name of hierarchal ELM or H-ELM with the combination of RL. The application was goal localization that is used in indoor navigation system. In order to resolve the two issues of convergence speed and universal approximation to the value function, an ELM was used by [30]. In their work, they have presented a new variant of ELM named called online fitted policy iteration (OFPI) where ELM was used to train the NN for value function approximation. In the work of [31], the challenges of using batch learning Neural Networks (NN) such as extreme learning machine were tackled. Also, he proposed Extreme Learning Machine (ELM), based on concept of Receding Horizon Cache RHC which is structure is designed to collect training data for NN by dynamically archiving state-action pairs and actively updating their Q-values. The model was named as ELM based RL (RHC-ELM-RL).

Another direction of combining RL with neural network is the usage of deep neural network such as its application in Arcade Learning Environment (ALE) [32] where the authors have attempted to evaluate the importance of key representational biases encoded by Deep-Q networks by proposing simple linear representations. Some researchers have improvement such networks from the perspective of the type activation functions such as the work of [33] where two activation functions for

neural network function approximation in reinforcement learning: the sigmoid-weighted linear unit (SiLU) and its derivative function (dSiLU).

4. METHODOLOGY

This section provides the developed methodology for OSELM based Q-learning. We present the problem formulation in sub-section 4.1. Next, the framework of OSELM-RL is provided in sub-section 4.2. Next, the algorithm of OSELM-RL is presented in sub-section 4.3.

4.1. Problem Formulation

We assume an agent A, an environment E, the agent controls the environment using set of actions $a = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ and the environment can take any state from set of possible states $s = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m\}$. Assuming that the environment E is at moment t in a state $s_{t,j} \in s$ and the agent provides at an action $a_{t,i} \in a$, then the environment will move to a new state $s_{t+1,k} \in s$. We assume that at each pairs of action state $(a_{t,i}, s_{t,j})$ have Q value that is calculated based on the reward function where after selecting the action the transition to the new state will generate a reward r_{t+1} and Q is just the accumulated reward. The agent will select the action that maximizes the accumulated reward or Q.

Example 1:

We assume an environment E that represents a maze as shown in Figure 1. The environment is combined of 14 states $s = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14\}$. The Actions that are allowed to the agents are $a = \{\text{Right, Left, Up, Down, UP Right, UP left, Down Right, Down Left}\}$. We assume also, that the agent will be rewarded for any action with a reward -1 in case the action does not lead to collision with the wall or entering the trap. Also, we reward the action that leads to collision with the wall with a reward of -10. The goal is to select the path that leads to the final state with the maximum reward. Assuming that at moment t , the state was 3, taking an action of Down will lead to entering the trap and finishing the game, while taking an action of Right will lead to a new reward of -1. Also, taking an action of UP will lead to a reward of -10. At any moment, we need the action that maximizes the accumulated reward. For example, for the sequence of actions of (Right, Right, Right, Right, Down, Down Left) the Q value is -6 while for the sequence of actions (Down Right, Down Right) the Q value is -2 which represents the maximum possible Q value or the optimal solution of the problem.

Home point 1	2	3	4
5	6	Trap	7
Trap	8	Exit 9	10
11	12	13	14

Figure 1. The maze is combined of 14 states, the starting state is at home point yellow, the final state is at state 9 green, while there are two traps that finish the game.

4.2. Framework of OSELM based Q-learning (OSELM-QL)

We propose employing an online sequential extreme learning machine to train a neural network on the optimal action or the action that provides the reward that maximizes the Q value which represents the accumulated reward given the environment is at moment t in a state S_t . The framework is provided in Figure 2. As we observe, the framework incorporates a neural network OSELM that trains at each moment, on the predicted final Q that results from taking an episode of certain value of epsilon and epsilon decay. Thus, the agent will use the online trained NN in order to predict the epsilon and epsilon decay that maximizes the reward as well as the accumulated reward Q. The framework is depicted in Figure. 2. As we observe, the agent provides an action to the environment and receives the corresponding reward and the new state. On the other side, the agent is responsible of training a neural network on the state action pairs and predicted Q value which represents the accumulated state. For training the neural network, online sequential extreme learning machine.

Figure 2. The framework of RL based OSELM or OSELM-QL.

4.3. Algorithm of (OSELM-QL)

The algorithm of OSELM-QL is provided in Table 3., The algorithm executes for the number of episodes that is determined in the input. In each episode, it starts with an initial state and arbitrary Q table, it takes the candidate actions, then it consults with the NN in order to predict the Q value for the set of actions. Next, the action that provides the highest Q value is selected and it is fed into the environment. Then the reward and state are updated, then the Q table is updated. Next, it is used for updating the learning of the neural network in a sequential way.

Table 3. Pseudocode of OSELM-QL

<p>Input Initial State NumberOf Episodes candidate actions NN // neural network Initial Q table Output Trained NN using OSELM Start 1. for each episode of ε and $d\varepsilon$ 2. repeat until final state 3. predict Q for candidate actions using OSELM 4. take an action that maximizes Q 5. update reward, state and Q in Q table 6. online training to NN using updated Q table End End</p>
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5. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

The evaluation measures for the developed approach are two types: the first one are RL related and the second type are application related. For the first one we use the number of iterations until the convergence to the final state and the value of the objective function that is optimized using the RL after optimizing. For the second, the measures are related to the nature of application. For example, in control application the steady state error, overshoot percentage and settling time are used. In network load balancing, the steady state discrepancy is used

We use inverted pendulum for evaluating our developed OSELM-RL learning. It is a control problem for non-linear control problem which is the inverted pendulum. This is a famous control problem where we have a motor controlling a plat and an inverted pendulum. The moving of the plate has two opposite directions right and left. The goal is to balance the pendulum which means an angle of 0 degree with a vertical y axis. The action is the moving command of the plat: right or left. The state is the current angle of the pendulum with the vertical y axis and the derivative of the angle. In order to evaluate the proposed integrated online sequential extreme learning machine with Q-learning or OSELM-QL, we generate a profile of data based

on set of experiments, in each one the inverted pendulum was running under different value of epsilon ϵ and different value of epsilon decay $d\epsilon$, and we record the Q value of the

system that is corresponding to each one them. The role of the OSELM-QL we show part of the data in Table 4. is to train sequentially on the values of Q based on given epsilon and epsilon decay and to predict the final Q value. This will lead to continuously update the two values to the range of increasing the final Q.

Table 4. the values of epsilon ϵ and epsilon decay $d\epsilon$ and the corresponding Q value for part of the data

epsilon	decay epsilon	Final Q
0.505491734	1.004068965	1.254500402
0.513241758	0.996580396	1.196195899
0.521897585	0.987795869	1.151172097
0.531031546	0.979093066	1.158840388
0.537831107	0.966998154	1.085135682
0.545618329	0.957940798	1.065837731
0.552644667	0.940509266	0.995547752
0.561922663	0.931146979	0.981081043
0.57030415	0.919585599	0.963270284

In order to show the performance of the prediction we provide the curve of prediction against the true value in Figure 3.

Figure 3. the predicted final Q value based on epsilon ϵ and epsilon decay $d\epsilon$ and the corresponding Q value

Analyzing the figure, we see that in the beginning, the OSELM model has a deviated predicted values from the true. However, the deviation decreases as the progress continues. This shows the capability of the OSELM to approximate the relation between the two values ε , $d\varepsilon$ and the corresponding final Q value for the model. Hence, using OSELM as an integrated block with Q-learning provides more adaptability to the dynamics of various types of experiments. Another observation is the oscillating pattern in the change of Q value from one episode to another which is represented by the balance between exploitation that increases the Q value gradually and the exploitation that might deviate the Q value in the curve.

6. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a new idea of balancing between exploration and exploitation in Q-learning using generated profile of episodes conducted according to change of values of ε and $d\varepsilon$. It uses a profile of episodes with assigning a different value of ε , $d\varepsilon$ for each episode. This is done based on learning the best model configuration that balances between exploration and exploitation and predicting the final Q value for certain configuration using the gained experience. A simulation result validates this approach as the predicted value converges to the true value after certain episodes. Future work is to apply this proposed OSELM-QL on actual learning the relation between ε , $d\varepsilon$ and the Q value. Another future work is to extend the model to include other parameters for optimization such as the learning rate and the discount factor.

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